

have been chemically investigated. In view of the toxic nature of the plant, studies were undertaken on its chemical constituents and the presence of myricyl alcohol, β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol, free β -sitosterol, emodin, aloe-emodin and quercetin is reported here.

Experimental

Powdered plant material (1.2 kg) was extracted with alcohol (95%) by percolation at room temperature. The alcoholic extractive was separated into petroleum ether (40-60°) and benzene soluble fractions. These fractions were chromatographed separately on Brockman's neutral alumina and silica-gel columns, respectively. Elution of the columns with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following crystalline compounds.

Petroleum Ether extract :

Myricyl alcohol—Eluted with petroleum ether and crystallized from benzene, as colourless microcrystalline compound (260 mg), m.p. and mixed m.p. (with an authentic sample) 85–87°, $(\alpha)_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1.3%) IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3460 cm^{-1} and formed an monoacetate m.p. 70-71°.

β -sitosterol—(Pet. ether: benzene, 1:1). It crystallised from acetone (charcoal) as colourless needles (650 mg) m.p. 136-37°, $(\alpha)_D^{20} -33^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1%) and showed positive tests for sterol: IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3420, 2920, 1470, 1370, 1055, 1030, 810 cm^{-1} . It formed an acetate m.p. 128-29° $(\alpha)_D^{20} -37^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 1.2%) and was identified as β -sitosterol in the usual way.

β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol δ : (ethyl acetate : ethanol :: 1:9). It crystallised from excess of ethanol (charcoal) as colourless crystalline product (430 mg) m.p. 270°-72°, IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3500, 2980, 2930, 1460, 1385, 1370, 1060 cm^{-1} and gave positive L-B and Molisch's tests. It formed an acetate (acetic anhydride and sodium acetate fused) m.p. 170°. On hydrolysis (alcoholic HCl 7%, 5 hr), it yielded β -sitosterol and glucose (paper co-chromatography) in two solvent systems butanol : acetic acid : water :: 4 : 1 : 5 and butanol : pyridine : water :: 3 : 1.5 : 1 using aniline phthalate as detecting reagent). Mixed m.p. with authentic β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol was not depressed.

Benzene extract :

Emodin—eluted with acetone and crystallised from ethanol as orange yellow needles (120 mg) m.p. 259-60°. It gave magenta colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and cherry red colour with aqueous alkali solution characteristic of emodin: IR : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3390, 2930, 1675, 1630, 1570, 1040, 768, 730 cm^{-1} . The compound was identified as emodin by its direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Aloe-emodin (acetone-alcohol, 1:1) was obtained as orange yellow crystalline product (65 mg) m.p. 222-23°.

Remaining alcoholic extractive was hydrolysed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid (7%, 3 hr). On extraction with ether, it gave a yellow product, which crystallized from acetone: methanol (1:1) mixture as yellow needles (170 mg) m.p. 310-312°. The compound answered tests for flavonols and formed an acetate (acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate) m.p. 194-95°. Identity of the compound with quercetin was confirmed by paper chromatography in two solvent systems (butanol: acetic acid: water :: 4 : 1 : 5 and butanol saturated with water), mixed m.p. determination and spectral data.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor R.H. Thomson, Aberdeen University for very kindly providing authentic samples of emodin and aloe-emodin, to the Heads, PAR and WEC Divisions for facilities and to the Director, I.G.F.R.I., Jhansi for kind encouragement.

References

1. J. P. DUTHIE, "Flora of the Upper Gangetic plains" (Botanical Survey of India) 1960, 2, 158.
2. R.N. CHOPRA, R.L. BHADWAR and S. GHOSH, "Poisonous plants of India" (ICAR publication) 1965, p. 41.
3. J. W. FAIRBAIRN and F. J. EL-MUHTADI, *Phytochem.*, 1972, 11 (1), 263-68.
4. J. S. AGARWAL, R. P. RASTOGI and O. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45 (17), 619.

Complexes of Copper(II) with Ethyl- β -Arylaminoacetonates

A. C. DESAI and C. M. DESAI

P. T. Sarvajanik College of Science, Surat

Manuscript received 29 October, 1976, revised 5 April 1977, accepted 3 June 1977

ETHYL- β -arylaminoacetonates are bidentate and get coordinated to copper from C=N nitrogen and C=O oxygen, the other two positions being linked to two halogens giving a six membered ring complex :

Such copper complexes are more stable towards water and sodium carbonate and have lower melting points when compared with zinc, cadmium and mercuric chloride complexes which decompose on air exposure¹; while the former darken on light exposure

TABLE-1

Ethyl- β -arylamino-crotonate -CuCl ₂ complex	M. P. with Decomposition	Magnetic moment in B.M.	MW		% Chloride		% Copper		Molar conductance in mhos
			Rast's method Obs.	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1anilino . .	138-140°C	*1.54	385	339.5	20.79	20.91	18.61	18.71	16.64
22-methyl-anilino . .	111-115°C	1.56	396	353.5	20.22	20.08	17.85	17.99	17.54
33-methyl-anilino . .	119-121°C	1.55	392	353.5	20.16	20.08	17.76	17.99	17.96
44-methyl-anilino . .	131-132°C	1.57	374	353.5	20.12	20.08	17.96	17.99	18.00
53-chloro-anilino . .	152-153°C	1.50	405	373.9	18.82	18.99	16.79	16.94	17.78
64-chloro-anilino . .	149-150°C	1.50	396	373.9	18.84	18.99	16.86	16.94	17.96

due to photo oxidation-reduction². The spectrophotometric measurements using Job's method, mole ratio method and slope ratio method indicate the composition of the complexes as 1 : 1³.

These complexes have been prepared by mixing equimolar (0.03M) alcoholic solutions of the chloride and the respective crotonate, when fine green crystals separated after half an hour. They are sparingly soluble in alcohol. Their magnetic moments were determined by using Guoy method and copper and chlorine by the usual methods. The analytical data are given in the table-1.

The low conductance values indicate their non-electrolytic nature and lower magnetic moment values have been attributed to dimerisation and some degree of dimerisation has been supported by molecular weight data; such lowering in paramagnetism of Cu(II) complexes is known⁴. The probable structure of the complex is a square plane, copper(II) with d⁹ configuration. The absorption spectrum in alcohol shows a broad band at 540 nm in agreement with D_{4h} symmetry of the Cu(II) complex.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (ACD) is thankful to the college authority for providing research facilities and feels grateful to Dr. P. K. Bhattacharya for guidance (M. S. University, Baroda).

References

1. V. M. THAKORE and R. C. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 26, 251.
2. Photochemistry of Coordination Compounds by Balzani and Carasity, Academic Press, 1970, p. 270-277.
3. A. C. DESAI and C. M. DESAI, *South Gujarat University Journal*, 1975, 4, 71.
4. G. A. BARCLAY and B. F. HOSKINS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1979; E. VHLIG and D. SEHVEIDER; *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1964, 90, 333; T. VEKI, T. ASHIDA, Y. SASADA and M. KAKUDA; *Acta. Cryst.*, 1967, 22, 870.

Dyes as Inhibitors for the Hydrogen Peroxide Decomposition

AJIT K. BANTHIA, SANKAR BISWAS and SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032.

Manuscript received 17 November 1976, accepted 3 June 1977

HYDROGEN peroxide is a unique metabolite normally produced and destroyed by a wide variety of plants and animals¹. Recently it has been suggested that cancer may originate by the action of an agent which directly or indirectly generates abnormally high concentration of H₂O₂ in the biological system². Furthermore, the lethal function of the biological poisons, which are known to inhibit the decomposition of H₂O₂, can also be attributed to the increase of H₂O₂ concentration in excess of lethal doses³. As very many dyes are well known either as biological poisons or as carcinogens, it is worthwhile to study their effect on the acceleration⁴ as also on the inhibition of H₂O₂ decomposition. In this preliminary note we report the inhibitory power of several groups of dyes viz. phthaleins, triphenyl methanes, thiazines etc.

Experimental

To have an idea of the inhibitory power of the dyes (listed in Table 1) we measured the rate of oxygen evolution from hydrogen peroxide solution both in the presence and absence of dyes under similar conditions and specially at the same pH (viz., pH 7) to avoid any pH effect. To verify the inhibitory power of the dyes from a different angle we measured the H₂O₂ concentration iodometrically in the original and final solutions. The changes in O.D values were determined by a Hilger U V speck spectrophotometer. It is evident from Table 1 that these dyes are very effective inhibitors for H₂O₂